

1 **Sea surface temperature variation in South China Sea between the Last Glacial Maximum**
2 **and the Holocene constrained by carbonate clumped isotope thermometry in foraminifera**

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24 Table 1. Non-linearity in the source of the mass spectrometer presented based on water equilibrated
 25 and heated gas data since December 2013. CO₂ used for equilibration was AS-2 CO₂ ($\delta^{13}\text{C} = -$
 26 32.62 ‰ and $\delta^{18}\text{O} = -4.67 \text{ ‰}$) and CO₂ produced from laboratory marble by acid digestion ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$
 27 $= 3.46 \text{ ‰}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O} = -5.73 \text{ ‰}$). Approximate $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of the water used for equilibration is
 28 also given. Working gases used were AS-2 CO₂ during 2013-2014 and Oztech CO₂ from Jan, 2015
 29 onward. Empirical Transfer Functions for different set of calibrations at different times are given
 30 at the right most column.

Temperature of equilibration	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (VPDB)	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (VPDB)	δ^{47} (WG)	Raw Δ_{47}	Empirical Transfer Function
December, 2013; $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of waters in VSMOW scale : -106‰, -25‰, and +22 ‰					$\Delta_{47-ARF} = 1.0996\Delta_{47-0} + 0.9145$
Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 17 °C	-32.62	-105.56	-105.758±0.014	0.150±0.017	
	-32.61	-105.14	-105.764±0.013	0.150±0.012	
	-32.69	-23.52	-21.680±0.015	0.006±0.012	
	-32.72	-23.20	-21.342±0.011	0.001±0.011	
	-32.63	22.06	24.405±0.018	-0.067±0.018	
	-32.56	22.06	24.063±0.016	-0.060±0.013	
Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 32 °C	-32.65	-108.91	-103.403±0.014	0.224±0.013	
	-32.65	-108.87	-103.463±0.016	0.216±0.010	
	-32.68	-108.87	-103.439±0.010	0.226±0.010	
	-32.71	-26.06	-19.113±0.017	0.075±0.017	
	-32.68	-26.04	-18.975±0.015	0.081±0.015	
	-32.59	-26.05	-19.045±0.022	0.085±0.022	
	-32.60	19.49	27.554±0.012	0.001±0.012	
	-32.62	19.34	27.386±0.015	0.012±0.015	
	-32.32	-91.12	-93.079±0.014	-0.650±0.015	
	-31.20	-87.65	-91.135±0.005	-0.650±0.008	

Heated CO ₂ at 1000 °C in quartz tubes	-32.33	-89.93	-88.914±0.010	-0.655±0.012	
	-31.95	-27.90	-21.838±0.013	-0.770±0.014	
	-31.96	-27.71	-22.198±0.010	-0.769±0.014	
	-32.08	4.97	15.709±0.013	-0.836±0.014	
	-31.95	2.73	12.014±0.012	-0.826±0.014	
July-August, 2014; δ ¹⁸ O of waters in VSMOW scale: -106‰, -25‰, and +22 ‰					
Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 25 °C	-32.38	-108.48	-105.760±0.014	0.344±0.017	$\Delta_{47-ARF} =$ $1.1336\Delta_{47-0} +$ 0.9638
	-32.35	-108.51	-105.760±0.013	0.322±0.014	
	-32.39	-25.96	-21.680±0.015	0.038±0.016	
	-32.43	-25.59	-21.340±0.011	0.026±0.013	
	-32.51	19.33	24.405±0.018	-0.118±0.018	
	-32.33	18.79	24.063±0.016	-0.107±0.016	
Heated CO ₂ at 1000 °C in quartz tubes	-31.12	-87.67	-87.166±0.014	-0.521±0.015	
	-31.88	-89.95	-24.062±0.019	-0.770±0.019	
	-31.96	-27.91	-23.822±0.018	-0.739±0.017	
	-32.10	2.72	7.101±0.013	-0.830±0.009	
	-31.54	1.66	6.552±0.016	-0.857±0.015	
November, 2014; δ ¹⁸ O of waters in VSMOW scale: -106‰, -25‰, and +22 ‰					
Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 25 °C	-32.50	-104.90	-102.450±0.016	0.141±0.010	$\Delta_{47-ARF} =$ $1.084\Delta_{47-0} +$ 0.9446
	-32.53	-104.33	-101.900±0.008	0.135±0.008	
	-32.60	-24.31	-20.479±0.016	0.022±0.017	
	-32.56	-24.36	-20.243±0.013	0.024±0.010	
	-32.60	19.48	23.913±0.012	-0.062±0.008	

	-32.60	19.38	24.507±0.014	-0.062±0.013	
Heated CO ₂ at 1000 °C in quartz tubes	-32.46	9.95	-84.268±0.012	-0.722±0.009	
	-32.34	-11.56	-22.931±0.020	-0.814±0.014	
	-32.17	-12.62	-22.456±0.016	-0.808±0.017	
	-32.27	4.10	8.832±0.014	-0.868±0.012	
	-32.53	-25.73	6.317±0.012	-0.851±0.011	
February, 2015; δ ¹⁸ O of waters in VSMOW scale: -24‰, -7‰, and +21 ‰					
Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 25 °C	-32.69	-23.93	-35.960±0.017	-0.055±0.012	$\Delta_{47-ARF} =$ $1.0725\Delta_{47-0} +$ 0.9708
	-32.76	-7.11	-35.516±0.018	-0.052±0.017	
	-32.61	-7.07	-19.286±0.006	-0.038±0.008	
	-32.71	20.02	-19.027±0.018	-0.039±0.015	
	-32.72	19.98	7.911±0.013	-0.032±0.013	
Heated CO ₂ at 1000 °C in quartz tubes	-32.30	8.53	7.742±0.011	-0.057±0.008	
	-32.62	3.86	-38.649±0.015	-0.907±0.011	
	-32.65	-12.26	-38.472±0.012	-0.925±0.011	
	-32.63	-12.82	-26.859±0.012	-0.883±0.011	
	-32.67	-25.46	-26.818±0.014	-0.897±0.009	
	-32.64	-23.93	-8.959±0.008	-0.895±0.003	
March, 2015; δ ¹⁸ O of waters in VSMOW scale: -24‰, -7‰, and +21 ‰					
Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 25 °C	-32.70	-24.09	-36.469±0.012	-0.051±0.013	$\Delta_{47-ARF} =$ $1.0403\Delta_{47-0} +$ 0.9808
	-32.71	-23.94	-19.329±0.014	-0.082±0.011	
	-32.60	-7.10	-19.372±0.017	-0.065±0.015	
	-32.69	-6.98	8.352±0.009	-0.039±0.008	

	-32.73	20.06	7.944±0.006	-0.052±0.006	
Heated CO ₂ at 1000 °C in quartz tubes	-32.60	8.55	-38.632±0.008	-0.930±0.008	
	-32.61	3.85	-38.165±0.010	-0.910±0.009	
	-32.65	-12.29	-25.317±0.015	-0.913±0.010	
	-32.70	-12.85	-25.958±0.015	-0.931±0.014	
	-32.68	-25.48	-4.388±0.016	-0.923±0.013	
	-32.55	-25.10	-9.107±0.016	-0.910±0.013	
February, 2016; δ ¹⁸ O of waters in VSMOW scale: -55‰, -24‰, and +21 ‰					
Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 25 °C	-32.49	-54.49	-67.061±0.012	-0.2656±0.012	$\Delta_{47-ARF} =$ $1.0022\Delta_{47-0} +$ 0.9743
	-32.47	-55.35	-67.916±0.015	-0.264±0.014	
	-32.55	-23.25	-35.580±0.012	-0.158±0.013	
	-32.59	-23.51	-35.878±0.013	-0.151±0.013	
	-32.60	20.39	8.445±0.016	-0.028±0.012	
	-32.60	20.68	8.762±0.016	-0.022±0.015	
Heated CO ₂ at 1000 °C in quartz tubes	-32.60	-47.05	-60.532±0.012	-1.160±0.012	
	-32.97	-45.23	-59.028±0.008	-1.149±0.010	
	-32.99	-24.76	-38.374±0.011	-1.061±0.011	
	-32.78	7.73	-5.406±0.018	-0.968±0.018	
	-32.67	9.71	-3.291±0.013	-0.959±0.012	
May, 2016; δ ¹⁸ O of waters in VSMOW scale: -24‰, -7‰, and +21 ‰					
Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 25 °C	3.40	-23.54	-7.800±0.018	-0.049±0.017	$\Delta_{47-ARF} =$ $0.9988\Delta_{47-0} +$ 0.9341
	3.38	-23.54	-7.601±0.018	-0.039±0.017	
	3.42	-7.52	8.721±0.015	0.035±0.014	

	3.38	-7.34	8.954±0.012	0.029±0.012	
	3.48	20.33	37.941±0.014	0.149±0.014	
	3.40	20.58	37.952±0.009	0.143±0.009	
Heated CO ₂ at 1000 °C in quartz tubes	3.55	-24.20	-9.554±0.017	-0.968±0.017	
	3.54	-24.26	-9.554±0.016	-0.932±0.009	
	3.59	-10.49	4.688±0.009	-0.872±0.010	
	3.58	-11.91	3.189±0.009	-0.904±0.009	
	3.50	11.58	27.718±0.012	-0.800±0.012	
September, 2016; δ ¹⁸ O of waters in VSMOW scale: -24‰, -7‰, and +21 ‰					
Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 25 °C	-32.31	-22.46	-34.657±0.022	-0.25±0.018	$\Delta_{47-ARF} =$ $0.9941\Delta_{47-0} +$ 0.9863
	-32.24	-22.24	-34.353±0.018	-0.243±0.017	
	-32.51	-7.00	-19.184±0.012	-0.161±0.010	
	-32.58	-6.95	-19.202±0.015	-0.158±0.015	
	-32.53	20.71	8.893±0.012	-0.013±0.011	
	-32.32	20.51	8.871±0.015	-0.019±0.015	
Heated CO ₂ at 1000 °C in quartz tubes	-33.30	-24.37	-38.409±0.011	-1.189±0.012	
	-33.69	-24.30	-38.690±0.010	-1.168±0.010	
	-31.99	-19.09	-31.797±0.012	-1.133±0.010	
	-32.96	-14.04	-27.63±0.022	-1.126±0.021	
	-32.82	5.53	-7.656±0.016	-0.989±0.005	
	-33.25	5.40	-8.291±0.008	-1.029±0.008	
June, 2017; δ ¹⁸ O of waters in VSMOW scale: -24‰, -7‰, and +21 ‰					
	-32.50	-22.82	-35.200±0.017	-0.272±0.017	

Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 25 °C	-32.59	-22.49	-34.964±0.008	-0.269±0.009	$\Delta_{47-ARF} =$ $1.0583\Delta_{47-0} +$ 1.0005
	-32.46	19.19	7.400±0.013	-0.021±0.013	
	-32.40	-22.96	9.216±0.013	-0.027±0.009	
Heated CO ₂ at 1000 °C in quartz tubes	-33.08	-23.37	-36.750±0.013	-1.133±0.012	
	-32.73	10.93	-38.808±0.010	-1.131±0.011	
	-32.90	9.57	-2.284±0.017	-0.939±0.017	
	-33.09	-22.96	-3.839±0.007	-0.935±0.007	
July, 2017; $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of waters in VSMOW scale: -24‰, -7‰, and +21 ‰					
Water equilibrated CO ₂ at 25 °C	-32.50	-22.82	-35.200±0.017	-0.272±0.017	$\Delta_{47-ARF} =$ $1.0434\Delta_{47-0} +$ 0.9994
	-32.59	-22.49	-34.964±0.008	-0.269±0.009	
	-32.46	19.19	7.400±0.013	-0.021±0.013	
	-32.40	20.95	9.216±0.013	-0.027±0.009	
Heated CO ₂ at 1000 °C in quartz tubes	-32.93	-21.69	-35.297±0.017	-1.119±0.017	
	-32.85	-27.88	-41.521±0.012	-1.180±0.014	
	-32.63	5.64	-7.379±0.011	-0.978±0.013	
	-32.52	11.66	-1.158±0.017	-0.938±0.011	

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38 Table 2. Stable isotopic composition including Δ_{47} values of ETH standards measured during the
 39 sample measurements. ETH standards are the carbonates used for first international clumped iso-
 40 tope calibration. Δ_{48} and Δ_{49} values (see Eqs. 3 and 4), used for monitoring contamination in the
 41 sample is also presented in the last two columns. Consensus Δ_{47} values for ETH1 and ETH3 are
 42 0.293‰ and 0.701‰ at acid digestion temperature of 25 °C.

Sample	Date of measurement	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (VPDB)	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (VPDB)	δ^{47} (WG)	Δ_{47} (CDES)	Δ_{48}	Δ_{49}
ETH1	27/03/2015	2.18	-2.23	19.216±0.017	0.357±0.011	0.07	-93
ETH3	27/03/2015	1.84	-1.65	19.799±0.012	0.709±0.011	-1.8	-170
ETH1	11/8/ 2015	2.09	-2.20	19.049±0.012	0.307±0.010	-0.24	-36
ETH3	11/8/ 2015	1.78	-1.74	19.658±0.016	0.701±0.013	-1.1	-34
ETH1	30/8/2015	2.08	-2.46	18.840±0.016	0.310±0.008	-1.3	-99
ETH3	30/8/2015	1.77	-1.63	19.776±0.022	0.707±0.004	-1.0	-56
ETH1	5/9/2015	2.06	-1.98	19.281±0.016	0.309±0.014	-0.8	-41
ETH3	5/9/2015	1.79	-1.57	19.838±0.016	0.703±0.016	-0.7	-20
ETH3	14/9/2015	1.77	-1.65	19.701±0.013	0.675±0.011	-0.9	-42
ETH3	14/9/2015	1.84	-1.74	19.627±0.016	0.655±0.014	0.6	-45
ETH3	14/9/2015	1.79	-1.57	19.691±0.017	0.711±0.015	0.1	-73
ETH1	22/9/2015	1.82	-2.22	18.848±0.011	0.302±0.011	0.5	-104
ETH3	22/9/2015	1.96	-1.68	19.971±0.013	0.713±0.015	0.5	-70
ETH1	30/9/2015	2.07	-2.17	19.176±0.013	0.310±0.011	0.1	-26
ETH3	30/9/2015	1.71	-1.65	19.785±0.013	0.693±0.013	0.4	-65
ETH1	03/02/2016	2.05	-2.19	19.133±0.013	0.348±0.010	1.0	-115
ETH1	19/5/2016	2.19	-2.24	19.235±0.017	0.325±0.015	-3.2	-85
ETH3	19/5/2016	1.79	-1.69	19.808±0.014	0.715±0.008	-2.8	-50

ETH3	5/6/2016	1.73	-1.38	20.101±0.007	0.725±0.007	-1.6	125
ETH3	5/6/2016	1.73	-1.74	18.304±0.013	0.715±0.012	-1.7	109
ETH3	5/6/2016	1.71	-2.21	19.216±0.016	0.716±0.015	-1.4	31
ETH3	20/6/2016	1.74	-1.78	18.423±0.014	0.732±0.014	-0.1	46
ETH3	20/6/2016	1.64	-2.20	19.154±0.010	0.717±0.008	-1.4	117
ETH1	25/4/2017	1.92	-2.34	18.895±0.013	0.306±0.012	0.2	-67
ETH1	25/4/2017	1.86	-2.41	18.483±0.012	0.324±0.010	0.4	-8
ETH1	29/4/2017	1.79	-2.59	18.547±0.012	0.318±0.013	0.4	26
ETH1	29/4/2017	1.83	-2.68	18.406±0.014	0.353±0.010	0.4	66
ETH3	24/8/2016	1.83	-1.73	19.742±0.018	0.714±0.016	-1.3	-82
ETH1	15/5/2017	1.95	-2.32	18.874±0.012	0.290±0.012	0.4	-62
ETH3	23/6/2017	1.81	-1.76	19.807±0.012	0.739±0.011	-0.6	-49

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55 Table 3. Stable isotopic compositions including clumped isotope ratios for three selected planktic foraminifer species. The depth along
 56 with the radiocarbon ages and associated analytical uncertainties at 1 σ level are also presented.

Depth (cm)	Age (cal yr BP)	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (VPDB)	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (VPDB)	δ^{45} (WG)	δ^{46} (WG)	Δ_{47} (CDES) $\pm 1\text{SE}$	Δ_{47} (ICDES) $\pm 95\%$ CI	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) $\pm 1\text{SE}^*$
<i>G. sacculifer</i>								
57-59	1738 $\pm$ 39	1.99	-1.92	5.526	14.050	0.692 $\pm$ 0.017	0.656 $\pm$ 0.031	28 $\pm$ 6
132-134	4688 $\pm$ 39	1.94	-1.98	5.068	13.916	0.699 $\pm$ 0.014	0.685 $\pm$ 0.031	25 $\pm$ 5
134-136	4728 $\pm$ 39	1.96	-1.91	4.466	14.021	0.683 $\pm$ 0.015	0.672 $\pm$ 0.031	31 $\pm$ 5
206-208	7599 $\pm$ 39	1.74	-2.01	5.458	13.891	0.696 $\pm$ 0.019	0.687 $\pm$ 0.031	26 $\pm$ 6
240-242	8782 $\pm$ 34	1.87	-2.12	5.485	13.872	0.679 $\pm$ 0.015	0.689 $\pm$ 0.031	32 $\pm$ 5
360-362	13315 $\pm$ 33	1.79	-1.08	5.840	15.123	0.707 $\pm$ 0.009	0.682 $\pm$ 0.031	23 $\pm$ 3
456-458	15710 $\pm$ 1	1.51	-0.39	5.255	15.710	0.722 $\pm$ 0.016	0.688 $\pm$ 0.031	18 $\pm$ 5
484-486	16433 $\pm$ 26	1.57	-0.29	6.974	15.780	0.723 $\pm$ 0.017	0.319 $\pm$ 0.032	18 $\pm$ 5
518-520	17311 $\pm$ 26	0.67	-0.58	3.538	15.070	0.705 $\pm$ 0.011	0.704 $\pm$ 0.031	23 $\pm$ 4
576-578	18808 $\pm$ 22	1.38	-0.52	5.064	15.547	0.723 $\pm$ 0.017	0.676 $\pm$ 0.031	18 $\pm$ 5
708-710	21354 $\pm$ 19	1.54	-0.60	5.288	15.565	0.720 $\pm$ 0.008	0.681 $\pm$ 0.031	19 $\pm$ 2
710-712	21388 $\pm$ 12	1.58	-0.51	5.717	15.556	0.718 $\pm$ 0.018	-0.349 $\pm$ 0.031	20 $\pm$ 6
826-828	21923 $\pm$ 4	1.78	-0.81	5.388	14.860	0.729 $\pm$ 0.023	0.763 $\pm$ 0.031	16 $\pm$ 7
847-849	22008 $\pm$ 10	1.49	-0.62	5.164	15.461	0.740 $\pm$ 0.016	0.748 $\pm$ 0.031	13 $\pm$ 5
<i>G. ruber</i>								
132-134	4688 $\pm$ 39	1.39	-2.27	4.181	13.744	0.687 $\pm$ 0.010	0.627 $\pm$ 0.031	30 $\pm$ 3
206-208	7599 $\pm$ 39	1.32	-2.32	3.873	13.617	0.711 $\pm$ 0.014	0.456 $\pm$ 0.031	22 $\pm$ 4
238-240	8713 $\pm$ 34	0.74	-2.43	4.430	13.425	0.704 $\pm$ 0.013	0.721 $\pm$ 0.031	24 $\pm$ 4
360-362	13315 $\pm$ 33	1.08	-1.63	4.818	14.449	0.703 $\pm$ 0.012	0.661 $\pm$ 0.031	24 $\pm$ 4
403-405	14538 $\pm$ 24	0.89	-1.01	4.770	15.046	0.729 $\pm$ 0.015	0.719 $\pm$ 0.031	16 $\pm$ 4
456-458	15710 $\pm$ 1	0.99	-0.83	4.817	15.302	0.719 $\pm$ 0.028	0.684 $\pm$ 0.031	19 $\pm$ 9
576-578	18808 $\pm$ 22	1.02	-0.78	4.671	15.373	0.726 $\pm$ 0.009	0.683 $\pm$ 0.031	17 $\pm$ 3
710-712	21388 $\pm$ 12	1.07	-0.78	4.385	15.295	0.716 $\pm$ 0.004	0.657 $\pm$ 0.031	20 $\pm$ 1
748-754	21576 $\pm$ 9	0.90	-1.01	4.614	14.767	0.744 $\pm$ 0.019	0.755 $\pm$ 0.031	12 $\pm$ 5
<i>G. menardii</i>								
7-9	1000 $\pm$ 24	1.876	-0.076	5.352	15.968	0.697 $\pm$ 0.060	0.718 $\pm$ 0.031	26 $\pm$ 7

57-59	1738±39	1.957	-0.219	5.530	15.753	0.700±0.036	0.72±0.031	25±4
134-136	4728±39	1.878	0.001	5.605	16.083	0.690±0.042	0.704±0.031	29±5
206-208	7599±39	1.816	-0.291	5.574	15.964	0.689±0.030	0.709±0.031	29±3
360-362	13315±33	1.366	0.29	5.164	16.234	0.710±0.033	0.754±0.031	22±3
403-405	14538±24	1.464	0.928	5.225	16.867	0.703±0.033	0.725±0.031	24±4
456-458	15710±1	1.56	1.02	5.350	17.109	0.710±0.036	0.712±0.031	22±4
708-712	21354±19	1.621	1.199	5.234	17.258	0.723±0.060	0.777±0.031	18±6

57 *Temperature is estimated using Δ_{47} values in CDES scale and following Kelson et al. (2017) calibration

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67 Table 4. Mg/Ca ratios and corresponding temperatures with a few foraminifera samples from the
68 Holocene and the LGM

Depth (cm)	Species	Age	Mg/Ca (mmol/mol)	Temp. (°C)
Holocene				
240-242	<i>G. sacculifer</i>	8782±34	3.302	26.3
240-242	<i>G. sacculifer</i>	8782±34	3.898	28.1
Average				27.2
Last Glacial Maximum (LGM)				
604-606	<i>G. ruber</i>	19350±19	2.708	24.1
672-678	<i>G. sacculifer</i>	20699±38	3.117	25.6
Average				24.8

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85 Table 5. Ecological preferences of major diatom taxa in the studied samples from South China
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Taxa	Ecological preferences	References
<i>Asterolampra grevillei</i>	tropical	Krayesky et al. (2009)
<i>Azpeitia nodulifera</i>	typical oceanic, planktonic, warm tropical equatorial species	Sims et al. (1989); Jiang et al. (2004)
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp.	marine planktonic, generally associated with high-latitude regions, temperate coastal areas and upwelling systems	Garrison (1984); Crosta et al. (1997) Romero et al. (2012); Abelmann et al. (2006); Li et al. 2021)
<i>Coscinodiscus asteromphalus</i>	warm water form, marine species, sub-tropical diatom	Barron (1973)
<i>Coscinodiscus radiatus</i>	warm water form cosmopolitan, wide temperature tolerance	Barron (1973); Ren et al. (2014); Abrantes (1988, 1991)
<i>Ethmodiscus rex</i>	rare diatom species, present in well-mixed water, migrating vertically between the surface for photosynthesis and the nutricline to obtain nutrients	Xiong et al. (2015)
<i>Paralia sulcata</i>	centric, warm to cold water	Chakraborty et al. (2019)
<i>Rhizosolenia</i> sp.	sign of indicator of the presence of upwelling condition	Lock-Wilde et al., (2017)
<i>Thalassionema frauenfeldii</i>	cool water indicator	Plata et al. (2018)
<i>Thalassionema nitzschioides</i>	warm water form, sub-tropical diatom Warm water form, Low salinity, upwelling indicator	Barron (1973); Margalef (1978); Abrantes (1988, 2007)
<i>Thalassiosira lineata</i>	warm water form	Ren et al. (2014)

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Table 6: Stable isotopic compositions of the anchor samples used for conversion of the raw Δ_{47} values into ICDES scale

UID	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ wg	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ wg	δ^{45}	δ^{46}	δ^{47}	δ^{48}	δ^{49}	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (VPDB)	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (VSMOW)	Δ_{47} raw	Δ_{48} raw	Δ_{49} raw	Δ_{47} (ICDES)
ETH1													
1	-3.59	24.96	5.88	13.84	19.22	25.97	-142.43	2.07	37.03	-0.53	-1.86	-170.49	0.32
2	-3.59	24.96	5.76	13.90	19.13	29.13	-85.81	1.96	37.07	-0.55	1.10	-115.71	0.30
3	-3.59	24.96	5.89	13.84	19.24	24.56	-54.58	2.08	37.03	-0.53	-3.23	-85.52	0.32
4	-3.59	24.96	5.76	13.90	19.13	29.13	-85.81	1.96	37.07	-0.55	1.10	-115.71	0.30
5	-3.59	24.96	5.55	13.83	18.85	28.35	-74.48	1.77	37.02	-0.54	0.48	-104.43	0.31
6	-3.59	24.96	5.78	13.90	19.18	28.07	6.41	1.97	37.07	-0.52	0.08	-26.52	0.33
7	-3.59	24.96	5.79	13.88	19.09	26.81	-2.03	1.99	37.05	-0.60	-1.11	-34.66	0.26
8	-3.59	24.96	5.78	13.61	18.84	26.01	-69.85	1.99	36.86	-0.57	-1.36	-99.79	0.28
ETH3													
10	-3.59	24.96	5.58	14.43	19.80	26.98	-168.26	1.78	37.46	-0.21	-2.02	-196.12	0.63
11	-3.59	24.96	5.49	14.38	19.81	28.35	-17.19	1.71	37.43	-0.08	-0.60	-49.94	0.76
12	-3.59	24.96	5.55	14.35	19.75	27.51	-50.70	1.76	37.41	-0.16	-1.37	-82.34	0.68
13	-3.59	24.96	5.54	14.40	19.81	26.05	-17.64	1.75	37.44	-0.14	-2.88	-50.46	0.70
14	-3.59	24.96	5.70	14.38	19.97	29.54	-38.30	1.89	37.43	-0.13	0.56	-70.55	0.71
70	-3.59	24.96	5.51	14.31	19.69	29.23	-38.67	1.73	37.38	-0.14	0.39	-70.60	0.70
73	-3.59	24.96	5.46	14.43	19.76	29.47	-33.29	1.68	37.47	-0.15	0.38	-65.58	0.69
AS2 (see details in Laskar and Liang, 2016)													
74	-3.59	24.96	-26.77	11.30	-16.87	23.74	-86.99	-26.92	35.19	-0.06	0.98	-80.70	0.96
75	-3.59	24.96	-26.77	11.29	-16.92	23.82	-104.24	-26.92	35.18	-0.08	1.10	-98.03	0.95
76	-3.59	24.96	-26.79	11.23	-16.98	23.11	-83.45	-26.93	35.14	-0.07	0.51	-76.99	0.95
77	-3.59	24.96	-26.77	11.32	-16.87	19.89	83.63	-26.92	35.21	-0.07	-2.82	91.06	0.96
78	-3.59	24.96	-26.77	11.32	-16.89	19.58	84.56	-26.92	35.21	-0.09	-3.12	91.99	0.94
79	-3.59	24.96	-26.78	11.30	-16.87	22.63	0.19	-26.93	35.19	-0.04	-0.10	7.10	0.98
80	-3.59	24.96	-26.78	11.31	-16.85	22.63	-23.10	-26.92	35.20	-0.04	-0.13	-16.38	0.99
81	-3.59	24.96	-26.77	11.28	-16.98	23.96	-14.80	-26.92	35.17	-0.14	1.25	-7.96	0.88

82	-3.59	24.96	-26.77	11.28	-16.97	23.81	-45.53	-26.92	35.17	-0.13	1.10	-38.90	0.90
83	-3.59	24.96	-26.77	11.28	-16.92	21.78	-176.02	-26.92	35.17	-0.08	-0.89	-170.30	0.95
84	-3.59	24.96	-26.78	11.26	-16.96	23.70	-25.48	-26.93	35.16	-0.09	1.03	-18.67	0.93
85	-3.59	24.96	-26.78	11.26	-16.95	23.47	17.77	-26.93	35.16	-0.09	0.79	24.88	0.94
86	-3.59	24.96	-26.79	11.22	-16.99	23.63	81.67	-26.93	35.13	-0.08	1.04	89.32	0.95
Equilibrated CO ₂ at 25 °C													
87	-3.59	24.96	-0.12	-7.75	-7.80	-18.17	115.09	-2.61	20.96	-0.05	-2.77	132.42	0.92
88	-3.59	24.96	1.49	36.83	37.95	74.73	157.15	-2.54	54.15	0.16	-0.27	76.06	0.90
89	-3.59	24.96	0.45	8.36	8.72	15.02	48.67	-2.60	32.95	0.04	-1.73	31.17	0.93
90	-3.59	24.96	0.44	8.61	8.95	15.53	-48.83	-2.62	33.14	0.03	-1.74	-65.16	0.93
91	-3.59	24.96	-0.16	-7.52	-7.60	-17.32	35.31	-2.65	21.14	-0.04	-2.36	50.97	0.93
39	-3.59	24.96	1.52	36.76	37.94	74.71	-80.69	-2.51	54.09	0.18	-0.14	-145.02	0.92
40	-3.59	24.96	-25.76	37.08	8.89	74.81	17.20	-26.81	54.37	0.02	-0.66	-26.25	0.92
41	-3.59	24.96	-26.73	8.93	-19.18	15.86	-19.36	-26.81	33.43	-0.14	-2.05	-8.08	0.90
43	-3.59	24.96	-27.02	-6.54	-34.35	-15.55	33.16	-26.60	21.91	-0.23	-2.55	77.59	0.88
44	-3.59	24.96	-26.80	8.98	-19.20	16.07	106.57	-26.88	33.47	-0.14	-1.94	119.27	0.90
45	-3.59	24.96	-25.58	36.86	8.87	74.37	236.45	-26.64	54.21	0.02	-0.65	183.89	0.91
Heated Gas (1000 °C)													
46	-3.59	24.96	-26.64	10.10	-18.84	19.81	-2.13	-26.77	34.29	-1.02	-0.48	6.97	0.03
47	-3.59	24.96	-27.04	9.85	-19.49	20.15	167.25	-27.12	34.11	-1.01	0.35	178.98	0.04
48	-3.59	24.96	-27.09	9.81	-19.60	19.78	42.51	-27.16	34.08	-1.04	0.07	53.12	0.02
50	-3.59	24.96	-0.26	-8.46	-9.55	-20.19	22.53	-2.71	20.44	-0.97	-3.40	40.04	0.03
51	-3.59	24.96	0.19	5.45	4.69	9.04	354.05	-2.74	30.79	-0.87	-1.88	339.38	0.06
52	-3.59	24.96	0.15	4.01	3.19	5.59	364.91	-2.73	29.72	-0.91	-2.43	353.99	0.03
53	-3.59	24.96	-0.25	-8.53	-9.55	-20.12	54.03	-2.70	20.39	-0.92	-3.19	72.21	0.08
54	-3.59	24.96	1.07	27.87	27.72	54.99	45.93	-2.64	47.48	-0.78	-1.45	-10.19	0.03
55	-3.59	24.96	-28.09	-8.69	-38.41	-20.95	-15.68	-27.48	20.31	-1.18	-3.71	32.24	-0.03
56	-3.59	24.96	-26.58	21.65	-7.66	42.00	99.77	-27.06	42.90	-0.93	-1.70	85.20	0.06
57	-3.59	24.96	-28.45	-8.64	-38.69	-20.56	328.16	-27.80	20.35	-1.14	-3.42	393.22	0.01
58	-3.59	24.96	-26.98	21.51	-8.29	41.91	239.75	-27.42	42.79	-1.00	-1.50	224.21	-0.01

59	-3.59	24.96	-27.39	1.80	-27.63	0.68	113.93	-27.18	28.12	-1.11	-2.91	143.39	-0.01
60	-3.59	24.96	-26.67	-3.34	-31.80	-9.19	68.58	-26.39	24.29	-1.12	-2.54	107.09	0.00

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